

Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Ni(II)

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Mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II) with para amino salicylic acid as primary ligand and pyridine, β -picoline, 8-hydroxyquinoline and nicotinic acid as secondary ligands were synthesised. The compounds have been analysed and structures have been suggested on the basis of reflectance spectra, magnetic susceptibility and I. R. spectral studies.

KHADIKAR and coworkers have carried out extensive work on the complexing tendency of salicylic acid and nuclear substituted salicylic acids with several metal ions. Complex formation with pyridine and substituted derivatives have also been studied and compounds with composition $[ML_4]^{++}$ and $[ML_6]^{++}$ have been reported¹⁻³. In the present investigation adduct formation of pyridine, β -picoline, oxine and nicotinic acid with Ni(II) para amino salicylate has been attempted. The obvious interest in taking up this investigation is that besides synthesis, mixed ligand complexes are expected to provide valuable information on magnetic properties, electronic spectra, flexidentate behaviour of polydentate ligands and stereochemistry. Magnetic data and reflectance spectra of these compounds are discussed on the basis of ligand field theory and the bonding in the compounds has been suggested on the basis of I.R. spectra.

Experimental

The mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II) with para amino salicylic acid (PAS) as primary ligand and pyridine, β -picoline, oxine and nicotinic acid as secondary ligands have been prepared using the method described by Khadikar *et al*⁴. The composition of the complexes formed have been confirmed by elemental analysis and is given in Table 1.

Magnetic moments of all the compounds were determined at room temperature using Gouy Method⁵ and are found as shown in Table 1. Reflectance spectra were recorded on spectrophotometer VSU-2P using 1 cm cell length. Observed band positions with assignments are given in Tables 2 and 3. Spectrochemical parameters for these complexes are given in Table 4. I.R. spectra of the isolated complexes were recorded by using Perkin

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS

Sl. No.	Compounds	Colour	% metal		% Nitrogen		B.M.
			Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	
1.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	15.30	15.29	7.29	7.20	3.221
2.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	10.82	10.68	10.33	10.22	3.343
3.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Pico ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	10.29	10.23	9.82	9.81	3.212
4.	Ni (PAS).(Oxine).2H ₂ O	Yellowish green	15.02	15.00	7.16	7.07	2.890
5.	Ni (PAS)(Nico).2H ₂ O	Light green	15.92	15.84	7.59	7.58	3.229

TABLE 2 - OBSERVED BAND POSITIONS FROM REFLECTANCE SPECTRA

Sl. No.	nm		cm ⁻¹	
1.	320, 565, 690, 925		31250, 17699, 14493, 10811	
2.	390, 610, 700		25641, 16377, 14285,	
3.	340, 480, 615, 690		29412, 20833, 16260, 14493	
4.	390, 560, 660, 855		25641, 17857, 15151, 11696	
5.	330, 385, 580, 660		30303, 25974, 17241, 15151	

TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL BANDPOSITIONS (cm⁻¹) WITH ASSIGNMENTS

S.No.	Compound	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (ν ₁)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) (ν ₂)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P) (ν ₃)	$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1}$	$\frac{\nu_3}{\nu_1}$	$\frac{\nu_3}{\nu_2}$
1.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	10811	17860	31250	2.892	1.653	—
2.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	10640	16377	25643	—	1.535	1.566
3.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Pico ₂ .2H ₂ O	9743	16260	29412	—	1.669	1.808
4.	Ni (PAS) (Oxine).2H ₂ O	11696	17857	27920	2.388	1.528	—
5.	Ni (PAS) (Nico).2H ₂ O	10420	17241	30303	—	1.635	1.758

TABLE 4—SPECTROCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

S. No.	Compound	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)* aquo ion	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹) complex	$\frac{Dq}{B}$	Bo (cm ⁻¹)† gaseous ion	B (cm ⁻¹) complex	β
1.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	8500	10811	0.972	1080	1112	1.030
2.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	8500	10640	1.600	1080	662	0.616
3.	Ni (PAS) ₂ .Pico ₂ .2H ₂ O	8500	9743	0.890	1080	1095	1.014
4.	Ni (PAS) (Oxine).2H ₂ O	8500	11696	1.639	1080	713	0.660
5.	Ni (PAS) (Nico).2H ₂ O	8500	10420	0.961	1080	1084	1.003

* C.S.G. PHILLIPS and R.J.P. WILLIAMS : "Inorganic Chemistry" Vol. 2 (Oxford).

† B.N. FIGGIS : "Introduction to Ligand Fields", (John Wiley and Sons),

Elmer I.R. spectrophotometer model 577 (4000 cm⁻¹ to 200 cm⁻¹) by KBr disc technique.

Discussion

The perusal of Table 4 indicates that the mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II) taking para amino salicylic acid as primary ligand and pyridine, β-picoline as secondary ligands have the composition NiL₂X₂.2H₂O where L is primary ligand and X the secondary ligand. In case of oxine and nicotinic acid as secondary ligand, the composition is MLX.2H₂O.

Ni(II) complexes with coordination number six are always high spin complexes with either regular or distorted octahedral stereochemistries. The ³F Russel Saunders term splits into three components ³A_{2g}, ³T_{2g} and ³T_{1g} in order of increasing energy. Thus three spin allowed transitions are expected,

These three transitions are observed in the regions 7000-13000, 11000-20000 and 20000-28000 cm⁻¹ respectively. As a result of this the 10 Dq values in octahedral Ni(II) complexes are seen to vary from 6800 to 12700 cm⁻¹. In addition to these three transitions two spin

forbidden transitions to ¹E_g and ¹T_{2g} are sometimes observed. Thus transition to spin singlet level, ³A_{2g}→¹E_g, a band is observed in the region 11000-15000 cm⁻¹ while a band in the region 17000-22000 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ³A_{2g}→¹T_{2g} transition.

Band positions observed from the reflectance spectra of various complexes, studied in the present investigation, showed that in case of Ni (PAS)₂.Py₂.2H₂O, Ni (PAS)₂.Pico₂.2H₂O and Ni (PAS) (Nico).2H₂O the ν₁ band is not observed, however their presence in near I.R. has been indicated by the upward trend of the corresponding reflectance spectra. Because of instrumental range we could not locate the exact position of this band and therefore the theoretical band assignment has been made as described by Lever⁶. Similarly in case of Ni(PAS)₂.2H₂O the ν₂ band could not be assigned exactly and, therefore, here also the theoretical band assignment has been made as described by Lever⁶. The values of ν₁, ν₂, ν₃ corresponding to their transitions are given in Table 3. The ratio ν₂/ν₁, ranges between 1.53 to 1.67, which is characteristic of all the Ni(II) complexes having pseudo octahedral environments, suggesting thereby strong T_{1g} term interactions⁷.

In cas of Ni(PAS)₂.2H₂O and Ni(PAS)₂.Py₂.2H₂O a weak shoulder is observed near about 14000 cm⁻¹. This is probably due to spin forbidden transition ³A_{2g}→¹E_g as suggested by Jorgensen⁸. All these results, therefore, show that all the Ni(II) complexes,

studied in the present investigation, possess octahedral stereochemistries. $10 Dq$ and B values are calculated, as suggested by Lever and are recorded in Table 4. These values are in very good agreement with those reported for octahedral Ni(II) complexes⁷. In addition to these two parameters the nephelauxatic coefficient, β , has also been calculated. Based on the values of β , the nephelauxatic series is as under :

The magnetic moments for all the Ni(II) complexes are recorded in Table 4. The perusal of Table 4 indicates that these values are in the range expected for Ni(II) octahedral complexes. The ${}^3A_{2g}$ ground term can generate no orbital contribution. However, spin orbit coupling mixes the first excited ${}^3T_{2g}$ term into the ${}^3A_{2g}$ term, the mixing in effect being expressed quantitatively as :

$$\mu = \mu_o \left(1 - \frac{4\lambda}{10 Dq} \right)$$

where μ_o is the spin orbit coupling constant. Since λ is negative for Ni(II) complexes it follows that moment will be higher the lower the $10 Dq$ i.e. weaker the ligand is. The experimental magnetic moments lie usually within the range 2.9 to 3.3 B.M.; they are independent of temperatures and of small departures of octahedral symmetry. In the present investigation magnetic moments of the complexes fall within the range 2.89 to 3.34 B. M. The observed deviation in magnetic moments from the spin only value could be due to second order Zeeman effects between the ground state and the highest ligand field terms.

I.R. spectra of the compounds show the characteristic bands of hydroxy acids and the secondary ligands. In case of oxine and nicotinic acid complexes the bands in the neighbourhood of 800 cm^{-1} confirm that the water molecule is present as coordinated water in accordance with Fujita et al⁹. In other cases the bands observed at about 600 cm^{-1} may be assigned for the presence of lattice water in accordance with Nakamoto¹⁰.

In all cases M-O band is observed at about 400 cm^{-1} . The I.R. spectrum of pyridine shows the presence of characteristic bands of pyridine at 700, 598 and 400 cm^{-1} , the latter two are due to in plane and out of plane ring deformations respectively. Similarly, I.R. spectrum of β -picoline shows the presence of characteristic bands of β -picoline at 780, 700, 620 and 400 cm^{-1} .

In the high frequency region the pyridine vibrations show very little shift upon complex formation. However, those of in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformations are shifted to higher frequencies upon coordination to metal, and are observed at about 640 and 430 cm^{-1} respectively. The shifting of these bands to higher frequency region, therefore, confirms that pyridine and β -picoline, are coordinated to the metal ion. The M-P_{ij} and M-Pico stretching vibrations occur near about 230 cm^{-1} . In all the mixed ligand complexes the observed band in the neighbourhood of 500 cm^{-1} , according to Nakamoto, may be regarded as the evidence of bonding of nitrogen to metal ion. Thus, the tertiary nitrogen of pyridine, β -picoline, 8-hydroxy-quinoline and nicotinic acid is attached to the metal ion as a secondary ligand forming mixed ligand complexes in all cases.

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